

FAIR data for Earth Sciences

Interview with Marine Vernet (Ifremer) and Marko Kulüke (DKR)

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Julia

Hello and welcome to today's episode of Stories of Data - The Open Science Talk. I'm Julia -

Marie

and I'm Marie. Today we are introducing another success story of EOSC-Pillar. We talk with Marine and Marco about their project which is about FAIR data for Earth Sciences. Welcome Marine and Marco! Thanks for joining us today!

Julia

So, first of all, please tell us a bit about yourself and your connection to the European Open Science Cloud: How did your story with EOSC-Pillar begin?

Marine

I was working on other projects, and I was proposed to participate in the EOSC-Pillar project for Ifremer. I did not have at the time specific knowledge of FAIR or EOSC, but I was curious, and it has been a great discovery.

Marco

I was assigned to the project when I started a new job two years ago. Although I was familiar with the principles of FAIR Data, I had not heard of EOSC at the time. I think that's why activities like this podcast are very important.

Marie

Now, what do you do in EOSC-Pillar? Please describe your work?

Marine

I am mostly involved in task 6.2, that aims to demonstrate the usefulness of EOSC for the Environment and Earth system community.

Marco

My work in EOSC-Pillar is very diverse. Most of the time is dedicated to developing FAIR data processing and management solutions, which can be taken over by the community. Another important part of my time is dedicated to outreach work, such as workshops, video tutorials and things like this podcast.

Julia

Who benefits from your work?

Marco

Our Use Case targets all scientists and data analysts in the field of Earth Science.

Marine

All the activities from the EOSC-Pillar project will benefit scientists and data analysts from different European research communities, by facilitating through EOSC data and services discovery and access across borders and research disciplines.

Marie

What are your goals with the AGILE FAIR data for environment and Earth system communities use-case?

Marco

Our goal is to offer services that give easy access to the distributed data sources and to provide a web-based processing environment with examples for FAIR data processing.

Marine

Yes, we aim at setting up a Virtual Data Analysis Platform that proposes on-demand data visualization, browsing and processing services to users from environment and Earth system communities, using the PANGEO software pack.

Julia

How did you start the project?

Marine

The use-case activities were launched with all partners in 2020. The use-case is transnational, involving six partners from Germany, Italy, and France, from different research fields (ocean and earth system, climate) and type of expertise (data analysts, developers, computing centers...)

Marco

I joined the project a bit later. From our side we started with some stocktaking to see which FAIR services and workflows we already have and continued from there. We take the **R** in FAIR very seriously.

Marie

So the R stands for reusability of data.

Marco

That is correct.

Julia

Who are the users of your service?

Marine

The users are both scientists and data analysts working in the environment and Earth system research field that want to access, process and analyze climate and earth system data online, on remote facilities. Through our demonstrator, they can either access ready-to-use notebooks or re-use them to create their own Python scripts using the PANGEO software stack available on the Virtual Research Environment.

Marie

How do you ensure the sustainability of your work?

Marco

That's a tough question, because project funding comes and goes. The last project phase is dedicated to develop a business model to ensure the sustainability of our service.

Marie

Hm, thanks for the hint. So we should do an episode about business models for Open Science services!

Marine

Indeed, our use-case was meant as a proof-of-concept. A reflection is engaged to see how this type of service could be sustained in time. Anyway, the concepts that were explored in our use-case and the achievements we made will nourish future activities in different projects. I can cite, for example, at EOSC level, the FAIR EASE project that will start in September.

Julia

What are you proud of?

Marine

I am proud of the achievements we made as a task: We managed to develop a virtual data analysis platform, providing on-demand access and processing services for heterogeneous big data, facilitating inter-calibrations and integrated uses of all environment and earth system data.

Marco

That our task leaders managed to keep everyone engaged even though we had no personal contact.

Marie

What has been challenging?

Marco

For sure the lack of in-person meetings. If you communicate with colleagues from different countries and research fields there can sometimes be misunderstandings, which would be easier to solve in person.

Marine

I also think that more face-to-face meetings would have been good. And regarding our activities, we tackled different challenges: indeed, the data from our communities are very heterogeneous. They come from different data sources such as satellites or in-situ observations made through engines or sampling, but also experiments and (climate) models. They are therefore of different types, volumes and formats. And they are managed by a wide range of European research infrastructures in several distributed repositories. So allowing scientists or data analysts from different earth system research fields to discover, access and inter-process this data online was not an easy task. Doing so on remote facilities, without affecting data processing speed was also a challenge, especially considering the large and increasing volume of data we are dealing with.

But thanks to our team and to the inputs from the project we achieved great progress in this regard.

Julia

If you could tell people on thing about EOSC-Pillar, what would it be?

Marco

EOSC promotes an infrastructure for open science.

Marie

What would you like people to remember about your work?

Marco

That FAIR science always pays off, even if the initial work might be a bit more comprehensive.

Julia

Dear Marine and Marco, thank you very much for your time and wish you all the best for your future projects!

Marie

Yes, thank you very much! It was a pleasure to talk to you! I'm really looking forward to our next podcast episode, and I hope you listeners will join us for that!